

Industry of enterprises electricity in the system problems

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Annotatsiya

In this article, the characteristics of reactive power compensation in the ETT of industrial enterprises in the electric system problems, in addition to the circuit parameters given in the determination of the electric network mode, several mode parameters, including the active power in the electric system, active and reactive loads of consumers, in addition to the distribution parameters between the node voltage active-reactive power in the enterprise's electrical system was studied and researched from the parameters of the complex mode for all variable modes.

Kalit so'z

Active and reactive power, transformers, design process, complex optimization, natural method, Synchronous compensator, Synchronous drives.

The industry is reactive in the ETT of enterprises' power compensation features.

Reactive power compensation issue, people farm for big important have is, electric supply system useful work coefficient increase, his economic and quality pointers in improvement main of factors one is considered Current at the time reactive power of consumption growth asset power of consumption from growth much high is some in enterprises reactive upload asset to upload compared to 130 % is enough Reactive power electricity transmission lines across long to distances transmission, electricity supply system technical and economic pointers deterioration take will come.

Industry in enterprises reactive power main part asynchronous drivers (consumption being done common reactive 60-65% of power), transformers (20-25%), air electricity transmission lines, reactors, transformers (around 10%) and other electricity consumers consumption do

Active power, the electricity of station generators by work if it comes out, is reactive power. The station synchronous generators, synchronous compensators, synchronous conductors, condenser batteries, electricity transmission lines and thyristor reactive power sources by generation will be done.

In the electric supply system design in process, reactive power of the coefficient indicator with work to the goal is appropriate. Of the enterprise reactive power coefficient how to be energy system solution because it does reactive power compensation issue right when solved consumers, electricity transmission lines, electricity distributor devices, transformers, changers and generators own into a received system of work effectiveness is provided.

Reactive power electricity transmission lines and transformers through the transmission process, electric energy addition wastes, tension loss to increase and electricity supply to the system to go expenses to increase take will come.

1. Electric transmission lines and from transformers reactive power increase, as a result, additional asset power and energy loss happened will be. If R to resistance have has been electricity transmission line through R and Q powers active if transferred power losses as follows defined as :

$$\Delta P = I^2 R = \left(\frac{S}{U}\right)^2 R = \frac{P^2 + Q^2}{U^2} R = \frac{P^2}{U^2} R + \frac{Q^2}{U^2} R = \Delta P_a + P_p \cdot$$

So, reactive power electricity transmission from the line transmission as a result of, additional asset power losses ($\Delta P_p = \frac{Q^2}{U^2} R$) occur will be and his value Q of per square right is proportional. That's why for, electric stations from generators to consumers reactive power transmission to the goal according to it's not.

2. Active R and reactive X resistances calculated energetic system from the element R and Q powerful energies when transmitted, of voltage loss as follows found :

$$\Delta U = IR \cos \varphi + IX \sin \varphi = \frac{UI \cos \varphi}{U} R + \frac{UI \sin \varphi}{U} X = \frac{P}{U} R + \frac{Q}{U} R = \Delta U_a + \Delta U_p \cdot$$

This is where ΔU_a ; ΔU_p is an *asset* and reactive powers transmission with depends has been of tension loss.

So, reactive power transmission as a result electricity supply system in the element addition tension loss ($\Delta U_p = QX/U$) occurs being his quantity Q and X to right is proportional.

Enterprise electricity supply of the system big amount of reactive power with loading, air and cable electricity transmission lines section surface to increase and of transformers powers to increase take will come

Industry in enterprises reactive power from the energy system less acceptance of doing two the way there is :

- natural method ;
- special compensatory devices to use method.

First in line natural methods based on reactive power consumption to reduce seeing output because it is necessary in this big in quantity expenses demand will not be done.

Reactive power compensatory technical tools The following devices include condenser batteries, synchronous drivers or compensators and valved static reactive power the source.

Synchronous excitation of drivers (SYu). so that the amount from nominal when increased reactive power work is issued.

Synchronous compensator (SK) salt work mode working Syu is, on the axis mechanic upload won't be and he only reactive power work to issue intended.

Industry in enterprises condenser batteries a lot is used. They are 0.22; 0.38; and 0.66; to voltages of 6 and 10 kV intended is a building inside or output can Capacitors one or three phases by doing work is issued. The condenser of batteries reactive power in compensation wide to use main reasons of the following consists of :

- asset of power comparison waste up to 0.005 (kW / kVAr). small to be possible;
- exploitation and repair (assembly) works easily will be done ;
- the price is relatively cheap
- weight light
- without noise works ;
- electric consumers of the group are located near the field installation and can

Condenser batteries have three phases to the network triangle in the form of is connected. When connected each one in the element tension value star scheme according to connect relatively $\sqrt{3}$ times big to be and work being released reactive of power quantity and 3 times more than will be Capacitors from the network when disconnected residual charge automatic respectively asset to resistance discharge need Discharger resistance as at voltages of 6-10 kV two one phase tension transformers at a voltage of 0.38 kV flammable lamps is used.

Compensatory of devices necessary power to determine in time of the energy system to the enterprise transmitted reactive power the amount account get need General without the following a must execution demand will be :

$$Q_k \geq Q_h - Q_t \quad (kVAr)$$

here, Q_h - of the enterprise accounting (consumption does) reactive power, (kVAr) ;

Q_e - energy system by transmitted reactive power, (kVAr) ;

Q_k - in the enterprise being compensated necessary has been reactive power, (kVAr).

Of the enterprise reactive power shortage one part energy system by if covered, and the second part of the enterprise to be installed compensators is filled.

Compensatory of devices power as follows to determine an

$$Q_k = P_{um} \cdot (tg\varphi_h - tg\varphi_e) \quad (kVAr)$$

this is where, P_{um} - the energy system downloads the maximum when , of the enterprise asset power, (kW);

$tg \varphi_e$ - power system demand who does reactive power coefficient, (calculations for $\cos \varphi = 0.95$ has been in the case, $tg \varphi_e = 0.328$ to accepted as equal done).

Textiles factory for reactive power compensation event we will spend In this reactive power source as condenser battery we use

Enterprises electricity desired to be classified There are 3 types of tariffs :

1. Tariff 6⁰⁰ from 9⁰⁰ up to 1350 som for 1 kw of energy
 2. Tariff 9⁰⁰ from 17⁰⁰ up to 1 kW of energy 900 some for
 3. Tariff 22⁰⁰ from 6⁰⁰ up to 1 kW of energy 600 some for
- 1-quart Reactive power demand for 20.09 some*

This enterprise a day 2 million during sq asset power and 760 thousand Quar reactive power consumption by not coming

$tg \varphi = 0.38$ ha equal to

Enterprise specified 760 thousand Quar reactive 200-250 kvar more than power reactive power consumption is doing Of this as a result enterprise

$$tg \varphi = \frac{Q}{P} = \frac{960000}{2000000} = 0.48$$

$$tg \varphi = \frac{Q}{P} = \frac{960000}{2000000} = 0.50$$

compared to $tg \varphi = 0.38$ increased gone

Normal mode for power coefficient considered

$$S = \sqrt{P^2 + Q^2} = 2139532$$

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{P}{S} = \frac{2000000}{2139532} = 0.93$$

Normal mode didn't happen in case the power coefficient considered

$$S = \sqrt{P^2 + Q^2} = 2218468$$

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{P}{S} = \frac{2000000}{2218468} = 0.9$$

of the enterprise reactive power desired high that it was due, to the enterprise of 3 transformers installed each 800 sq. to one from condenser batteries installed.

Reactive power demand is managed for management remote control, condenser batteries step by step reactive power to install.

Of this as a result

$$tg \varphi = \frac{Q}{P} = \frac{750000}{2000000} = 0.37$$

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